

Supplement:

**Drug loading of inorganic calcium phosphate microcapsules
by solvent impregnation**

Christina Schröter, Christoph Meier, Maxim Puchkov, and Jörg Huwyler*

Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Basel, 4056 Basel, Switzerland

*Author for correspondence:

Jörg Huwyler, PhD
Professor of Pharmaceutical Technology
Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences
University of Basel
Klingelbergstrasse 50
CH-4056 Basel, SWITZERLAND
Tel ++41 61 207 15 13
Sec ++41 61 207 15 00
<https://pharma.unibas.ch>

Summary

Inorganic hydroxyapatite microcapsules (TIP or «templated inverted particles») were recently introduced as a novel pharmaceutical excipient, which can be used for the preparation of solid dosage forms [1]. They allow for cost-efficient preparation of orally dispersible tablets (ODT) by processing of drug loaded microcapsules using standardized unit operations. Drug loading can be achieved using particle impregnation. This has been successfully demonstrated using a wide array of chemically diverse drug substances [2]. Thereby, an exceptionally high loading efficiency can be reached due to a «capillary pumping» effect: the unique flask-like geometry of pores in the capsule shell efficiently attracts liquids and allows for an escape of trapped gas from the inner cavity. In contrast to commonly used «sponge-like» porous conventional drug carriers such as functionalized calcium carbonate [3] or mesoporous silica nanoparticles [4], complete filling of the inner void of the particles is observed resulting in, for example, $5.3 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$ of water uptake corresponding to 45% of total volume of the drug carrier.

The traditional workstream used for the preparation of tablets is depicted by green arrows in **Figure 1** and represents procedures established for large scale industrial production of tablets in compliance with GMP regulations. In this context, drug loading of microcapsules is the first step preceding or in parallel to granulation and followed by compaction. Thereby, fluidized bed technologies, for example, are expected to provide a high throughput and lead to maximal, i.e. complete, loading. However, a major shortcoming of this strategy is the costly and time-consuming design and validation of a GMP compliant tablet manufacturing process, which precludes small scale production of tablets or application of this technology in the field of individualized patient care. To address this limitation, we have therefore explored alternative production sequences (**Figure 1**, blue arrows). Best results were obtained with a novel drug loading procedure, which consists in impregnation of placebo tablets with drug product(s) and, if required, additional excipient(s) solved in a solvent of choice. Similar approaches have been proposed previously, however, with limited success due to poor loading capacity of conventional drug carriers or coating technologies, limitations imposed by non-compendial materials, or disintegration of the drug carrier during impregnation [5], [6], [7]. In contrast, our experiments carried out with pure compendial calcium phosphate microcapsules demonstrate that tensile strength of placebo tablets is not reduced after impregnation with high volumes (100% (w/w)) of solvent and subsequent drying thus demonstrating the feasibility of the approach (**Figure 2**).

Figure 1: Due to the exceptional solvent uptake capacity of TIP microcapsules, TIP powder as well as granulated TIP or placebo tablets can be impregnated with solutions containing active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) of interest. In contrast to the conventional tablet manufacturing process (green arrows), alternative manufacturing sequences can thus be implemented (blue arrows). This allows, for example, for a GMP-compliant preparation of tablets using placebo tablets as a starting material. Such placebo tablets can be combined with drugs of interest ad-hoc by simple solvent impregnation followed by a drying step. Thus, preparation at low scale of individualized dosage forms is possible at minimal costs. Intermediate to large scale production is possible using pipetting robots or impregnation by spraying of drug containing solutions.

Figure 2: Placebo tablets (200 mg, 1 cm diameter, 3 mm thickness) consisting of pure calcium phosphate TIP were impregnated with the indicated volume of solvent. Tensile strength was determined before impregnation and after impregnation and drying for 12 hours. Values are means \pm SD, $n \geq 3$.

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